

Exploring the Adaptability of Junior High School Students with Balikbayan Parents: A Phenomenological Study

Colobong, Kyrie Aliezon F., Garcia, Allyssa Jane B., Rabec, Khayla Greta Mae G.,
Valdez, Erika Therese D., and Divina, Leslie Doris M. Rpm, RGC

Abstract

Working overseas has become a common trend in the Philippines. With the parents being gone for a long period of time, this has caused their children to fall back on having to develop different coping mechanisms and changing perceptions upon their parents' return. This study uncovered the ability of the left-behind children of OFWs who are Junior High School students from Saint Mary's University to adapt with the changes in their lives brought by their balikbayan parents who return home temporarily in order to shed more light on this specific trend. The study utilized a qualitative approach, specifically the descriptive phenomenological method. This enabled the researchers to gain a deeper understanding regarding the perspectives of the left-behind children of OFWs about their parents. Through use of Colaizzi's Descriptive Phenomenological Method of analysis, Nine (9) key emergent themes were generated to explain the adaptation of the Junior High School students namely constant communication and pieces of advice, spending quality time, detachment, extended family and other support systems, understanding family set-up and acceptance, avoidance, adjustment and compromise, motivation and aspirations, and comfort and material support. This study may be imperative to future researchers, balikbayan parents, guardians, psychologists and guidance counselors as it offers insightful information regarding adaptation.

Keywords: Behavioral adaptability, Coping mechanisms, Cognitive adaptability, Emotional regulation, Left-Behind Children, Marian Coalition of Sons and Daughters of OFWs, Perceptions, Qualitative approach

Introduction

Change is inevitable. It is beyond the control of anyone, including parents and children. In the Philippines, working overseas or becoming an Overseas Filipino Worker (OFW) is a common trend. Aguilar (2021) emphasized that the Philippines is one of the biggest migrant sending-countries in the world and Asia's largest source of labor workers. This is another occurrence commonly called Brain Drain or Brain waste where skilled Filipino workers seek jobs abroad due to lack of job opportunities and low pay here in the Philippines. Many Filipinos have actually found this as a financial opportunity, enabling them to provide better for their families. Lobos et al. (2019) mentioned that working overseas has become a viable option to address the problems being encountered by one (1) out of twelve (12) Filipino families.

However, with OFWs being in demand in other countries, this also creates consequences for them and their left behind children. As mentioned by Montajes (2023), some of the commonalities of children in the Philippines are being separated from one or both parents, leaving them with non-parental caregivers or guardians. Malijao et al., (2023) also mentioned that parents being away can have an impact on their children, therefore it is important to establish a good relationship that is beneficial for the children of OFWs. With that being said, there would be moments where changes in the relationship of the balikbayan parents and their left-behind children happen. There are even certain occasions where the left-behind children experience certain symptoms of stress such as under-eating and headaches. Some of the common stressors of the children are missing their parents and feeling lonely, eating a lot, parents having high expectations and having a misunderstanding with friends among close friends, According to Navarro and Gorospe (2014). The study of Delima (2022), reported that there are certain themes that a child experiences being away from their parents such

as sources of anxiety from the safety and security of their parents, the feeling of anguish after their parents leaving, the challenges of readjustment or flexibility, changes in the dynamics of the parent and children, the children adjusting, as well as the non-OFW parent/ surrogate parents, extramarital affairs of their parents, the need for acceptance of their new reality and them doing their best to reciprocate their OFW parents' sacrifices. In addition to that, Shaw (2022) also emphasized that the time spent apart by the left-behind children from their mothers who are OFWs was utilized to cultivate vital connections with others such as their grandparents, aunts or siblings and even being close to best friends, romantic partners and confidantes. With that being said, it is indeed important for both the parents and their left-behind children to learn on how to adapt to these changes and still stay connected.

Adaptability

The study of Martin et al. (2013), stated that adaptability is appropriate cognitive, behavioral and/or affective adjustment in the face of uncertainty and novelty. Another from Wadleck et al. (2021), is that it is purported to be a key mental resource and refers to an individual's cognitive, behavioral and emotional regulation (adjustment) in situations of change, novelty and uncertainty. Saavedra (2024) also mentioned that adaptability is a skill of molding actions and reactions to the changing environment. Ibrahim (2023) mentioned that due to the rapid changes around the world, it is essential to have the skill of adaptability.

Adaptability of left-behind children

According to Machica and Montallana (2018), there are certain coping mechanisms of children such as being with their friends when they are being lonely and the use of dynamic communications such as facebook, messenger and so forth, to communicate often with their parents. Same with Taola et al. (2024), students cope with the absence of their parents by reciprocating their parents' efforts through good academic performance, understanding their parents' reasons for working abroad and building a circle of friends and family support system. In another article, from a Straussian grounded-theory study by Derasin et al. (2023) there are four themes that children of balikbayan parents go through. The first theme is the initial reaction, where the child feels resentment, desolation and withdrawal from their parents. The second theme is the impact of parental absence which includes yearning, envy of others, loneliness and even the lack of guidance from parents. The third theme is coping with parental absence, focusing on how the child copes with the absence of their parents, including strategies of diversion and seeking help from friends and family. Lastly, there is acceptance where the children just accept the circumstance and have the right perspective and appreciation for their parents.

Balikbayan Parents

Balikbayans are Filipino citizens who have been continuously out of the Philippines for a period of at least one year and Filipino Overseas Workers, therefore balikbayan is another term used for an OFW, According to the Embassy of the Philippines, amended by RA 9174. In a survey, according to the *Philippines Statistics Authority* (2022), it was estimated that there are 1.96 million OFWs who worked abroad from April to September 2022 and 7.1% of them are from Region 2. Montajes (2023) mentioned that there is an increase in the number of Filipino parents to work abroad due to economic reasons. Amoroso et al., (2023) also stated that due to the financial challenges and limited job offers here in the Philippines, parents are forced to work overseas, since it is their responsibility to cater to

the needs of their children. Another according to Delima (2022) is that more and more Filipinos go to other countries for greater opportunities and become OFWs, to provide a comfortable life for their loved ones.

Marian Coalition of Sons and Daughters of OFWs

Considering that having an OFW parent is common to children in the Philippines, Saint Mary's University has organized a group for the sons and daughters of OFWs for the purpose of group or individual counseling and for their empowerment and building a community since their parents are absent in their everyday lives. The sons and daughters of OFWs became a symbol and paragons of the Filipino youth, that despite the absence of their parents, they are still productive members of society, the church and of the school, to create a more unified dream that the youth is the hope of the nation. The students are automatically members of this organization, based on their personal inventory data.

Purpose of the Study

This study sought to:

A. investigate the phenomenon that occurred to the students of Saint Mary's University who have balikbayan parents. Specifically:

1. Profile of the students who have balikbayan parents;
2. The lived experiences of students who have balikbayan parents; and
3. The adaptability of students who have balikbayan parents.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative approach which is phenomenological study, specifically Husserl's Descriptive or Transcendental Phenomenology. The researchers utilized this approach to better explore and understand certain experiences in a deeper context, exploring reality to its fullest-undistorted and clear, which in this study, the adaptability of the children of balikbayan parents. With this method, the study was able to dive deeper into the experiences from the people who have gone through those situations from their perceptions.

In Husserl's (2019) phenomenology, it has a four-step process, including bracketing, intuiting, analyzing and describing. Bracketing is the act of identifying and setting aside preconceived ideas and opinions about the phenomena. Intuiting is for the researchers to maintain an open mind about the meanings that are attributed to the phenomena. Analyzing involved gathering themes, categorizing and giving sense to the phenomenon. Lastly is Descriptive, a critical step. The researchers then defined and understood the phenomenon in question, all according to Greening.

Research Locale

The data collection took place within the premises of Saint Mary's University (SMU) Junior High School Department, Saquing St., Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. SMU Junior High School and Science High School department was built on July 1, 1934 which follows the basic K-12 curriculum and added the Science High School on June 2, 1975 which has additional advanced subjects in Science, Mathematics and English. (SMU Official Site, 2024).

Research Participants

The respondents of the study composed of 15 students of the Saint Mary's University Junior High School, specifically from the Marian Coalition for Sons and Daughters of OFW (MCSDO). We cooperated with the Junior High School Guidance and Testing Office in screening the possible participants with the authorization from the principal's office. The researchers then visited each classroom to briefly inform selected students that they are candidates for the study and provided them with informed consent forms. Out of the 50 students that were screened, 16 students passed the screening process and were given consent forms. Students only became participants once the forms were signed by their parents. A total of 15 students submitted their consent forms and were interviewed by the researchers.

The participants are selected through the following criteria:

Inclusion Criteria

- A. Currently enrolled in the Saint Mary's University Junior High School Department in the academic year 2024 - 2025.
- B. Have either one or both parent(s) that are balikbayan; Overseas Filipino Workers that have returned or visited for at least two years in the Philippines.
- C. Students ages 12 to 15.

Exclusion Criteria

- A. Have either one or both parent(s) that are balikbayan; Overseas Filipino Workers that have returned or visited the Philippines for more than two years.
- B. Students' age must not be below age 12 or above age 15.

Research Instruments

The researchers employed the use of (1) Robotfoto Form and (2) a Researcher-Made Interview Question/Guide that elicited the responses relevant to the objectives of the study. The first part of the research instrument included the Robotfoto Form, a dutch term that entailed the cartographic sketch of the participants (Kelchtermans & Ballet 2002, as cited by De Guzman 2009). Various demographic variables such as name, gender, age, course and year, school, and the parent who is currently abroad is included in the robotfoto form to delve on the profile of the students with balikbayan parents. The students' names will be turned into aliases by the time of publishing for the participant's anonymity. The situations of change, novelty and uncertainty that happened upon the return of the student's OFW parent(s) is explored. The impact of the balikbayan parent, changes in life and relationship dynamic were encompassed in this section. Five (5) interview questions are included in this section namely 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6. The third section is directed on the cognitive adjustments that students made upon the presence of their balikbayan parents, particularly their insights and perceptions. This section of the interview guide comprised five (5) open-ended questions namely 5, 7, 8, 9 and 17. The fourth section in the researcher-made interview addressed the behavioral adjustments like behaviors, habits and routines that students adapted during the return of their OFW parent(s). This section included five (5) interview questions such as 10, 11, 12, 13, and 18. The last section in the researcher-made interview sought to understand the emotion regulation of the students with balikbayan parents. This section contained Five (5) questions namely 14, 15, 16, 19 and 20.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher began the data gathering by submitting the Interview questions to professionals or experts for content validation to check if it will properly elicit answers that are in line with the research objectives. After the validation of the interview questions, the researchers administered a letter to the Research instructor, Junior high school Principal and adviser of Marian Coalition of Sons and Daughter of OFWs for the approval of gathering participants for this study. Upon approval, the researchers proceeded in gathering respondents and their informed consent. After that, the respondents were scheduled for interviews needed for the collection of data of this study. Then, the completion of the robotfoto form and facilitation of the interviews occurred on the set date of the schedule agreed upon by the researcher and participant. Lastly, the data collected is then transcribed and interpreted using thematic analysis.

Results and Discussions

Section 1. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Table 1

Summary of Participant Demographics

Participant	Gender	Age Range	Grade Level
Anastasia	Female	12-15	7
Beatrice	Female	12-15	8
Clara	Female	12-15	9
Darcy	Female	12-15	9
Ellise	Female	12-15	8
Faith	Female	12-15	7
Gil	Male	12-15	8
Heart	Female	12-15	8
Ivy	Female	12-15	8
Jordan	Male	12-15	8
Katherine	LGBTQIA+	12-15	8
Lina	Female	12-15	9
Melanie	Female	12-15	7
Nika	Female	12-15	8
Olive	Male	12-15	9

Section 2. The Lived Experiences of Students with *Balikbayan* parents

The study found multiple themes entailing the experiences of the participants in relation to the family dynamics when their *balikbayan* parents are abroad and at home. The experiences of the participants that were found to be prominent in this study are namely daily struggles, open conversations and openness. daily check-ins, adjusting to separation, availability and unavailability, longing, emotionally distant, anxiety/nervousness, initial awkwardness, difficulties connecting, reconnecting and emotional connection, growing apart, indifference to changes, accustoming, shifting interactions within the family, insecurities, isolation, sensitivity of topic, precaution, distraction, independence, optimism, gratitude, awareness, discipline, feeling at ease/being laid back, consolation, finding support, unconditional support and lastly, financial support.

According to Corchado (2024), the ideal family dynamics is based on having an open and healthy communication, giving and receiving love, care and support, having trust and respect for each family member, giving time to have a bonding moment with each other, sharing the same values and goals and at the same time having to accept values and goals different from them, and lastly, having to resolve conflicts in a healthy and constructive way. In contrast to that, a family with one or both parent/s being physically absent or away from the family could greatly impact the family dynamics or change it completely. Children are the most affected in the shifting of these dynamics for they are more vulnerable. A parent's prolonged absence could cause emotional, developmental and educational concerns due to the lack of physical presence of the OFW parent (Gudoy, 2024). However, being a child with OFW parents also has its advantages especially on the economic and financial aspects in life. Mothers who are abroad provide for their children's financial needs like for education, food, clothings and in some cases gifts (Ramirez, 2024).

Section 3. The Adaptability of Students who have *Balikbayan* parents

Adaptability is a process wherein an individual accommodates their behavior, thoughts and emotions as a key protective feature of mental health against their ever changing environment. These changes may be fixed, seasonal, evolutionary, progressive or new all together (Gillette, 2022). Furthermore, Adaptability is not a fixed skill and may be developed on both a personal and organization level (EY UK, 2021). To further understand the adaptability of the participants, the adaptability process of the students with *balikbayan* parents are expounded in this section. The adaptability processes that are explored are: constant communication and pieces of advice, spending quality time, detachment, extended family and other support systems, understanding family set-up and acceptance, avoidance, adjustment and compromise, motivation and aspiration, and lastly comfortability and material support. Children of overseas Filipino workers (OFWs) rely heavily on adaptability, which is the capacity to change one's thoughts, feelings, and behavior in response to shifting circumstances (Gillette, 2022; EY UK, 2021). This section examined the several adaptation mechanisms that were seen in these kids, such as time management, support networks, and communication techniques.

Children benefit from regular communication with OFW parents because it offers them emotional support and direction. By bridging the gap, technology enables parents to communicate their concern and provide guidance (Gaspan and Sasot, 2024; Magantor, 2024). Participants like Olive and Gil appreciate the guidance they get, and Lina finds solace in talking to her parents about her scholastic experiences. Heart emphasizes her mother's encouragement. According to Taola et al. (2024), candid discussions improve the bond between parents and children. According to Pinzon (2021), Gaspan and Sasot (2024), and Taola et al. (2024), regular check-ins allow parents to stay up to date on their children's life. However, as Gil, Heart, and Darcy's experiences demonstrate, difficulties occur because of different time zones and hectic schedules (Burgos, 2020). Children value their parents' attempts to stay in touch despite these obstacles (Montajes, 2023). Even with frequent communication, emotional distance can still play a role (Magantor, 2024; Soriano et al., 2022), highlighting the necessity of continuous communication to improve relationships (Delima, 2022).

Spending meaningful time with OFW parents at home is crucial for reestablishing and strengthening family ties. As demonstrated by Darcy's experience, activities such as outings aid in overcoming early uneasiness (Delima, 2022; Agonos et al., 2015). Children show joy when their parents return, demonstrating the desire for a full family (Abenir, 2021; Pinzon, 2024; Delima, 2022).

Detachment may occur in children who have had little parental involvement (Gaspan and Sasot, 2024; Montajes, 2023). Ellise's story serves as an example of how desensitization can result

from extended absence. Whether they are at home or overseas, some individuals say their interactions with their parents have not changed significantly.

In order to provide both practical and emotional assistance, extended family members are essential (Cabrera and Lu, 2021; Amoroso et al., 2023). Faith and Ivy are among the participants who look to family members for direction. As demonstrated by Heart and Olive's stories, not all encounters are favorable, as family dynamics change based on the presence of the OFW parent. Delima (2022) highlights how crucial it is for OFW parents and kids to stay in touch.

Children of OFW parents receive consolation and material assistance (Pinzon, 2021). Ellise enjoys the presents her father gives her, while Anastasia and Faith cherish the emotional support of their parents.

The situation in their family is progressively understood and accepted by the children (Burgos et al., 2020; Gaspan and Sasot, 2024; Pinzon, 2021; Capol et al., 2024). Ivy and Ellise remember their developing awareness of their parents' predicament, while Katherine admits her desire for her father's presence.

Some children cope with the emotional challenges by avoiding the issue or distracting themselves (Gaspan and Sasot, 2024). Clara's nervousness and Faith's use of distractions exemplify this.

In summary, the process of adaptation among children of overseas Filipino workers (OFWs) is complex and influenced by a number of variables. The emotional landscape is characterized by the need for acceptance and possible detachment, even though regular communication, quality time spent during visits, support from extended family, and technology all play important roles in building resilience. In the end, the experiences demonstrate how the kids actively navigate the challenges of international families and how well they can adapt to the cyclical nature of parental presence and absence. The long-term effects of these adaptive techniques on the children's general well-being and family dynamics might be investigated in more detail.

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